

Sthanika Chikitsa in Prasuti Tantra and Stree Roga: Classical Concepts and Contemporary Relevance

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Abstract

Sthanika Chikitsa is an important therapeutic approach in Ayurveda for the management of various gynecological disorders. It includes local treatment modalities such as *Yoni Prakshalana*, *Yoni Pichu*, *Yoni Varti*, *Yoni Lepana*, *Yoni Poorana*, *Yoni Dhoopana*, *Kshara Karma*, and *Uttar Basti*. These therapies act directly on the affected site, helping to alleviate symptoms, restore Dosha balance, promote healing, and improve reproductive health. Due to the rich vascularity and absorptive capacity of the vaginal mucosa, these treatments provide effective local and systemic benefits. When performed under proper indications and aseptic precautions, *Sthanika Chikitsa* serves as a safe, cost-effective, and minimally invasive treatment option in Stree Roga.

Keywords: *Sthanika Chikitsa*, *Stree Roga*, *Yoni Vyapad*, *Uttar Basti*, *Yoni Pichu*, Ayurvedic Gynecology, Women's Health.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of women's health involves a wide spectrum of issues, including reproductive health, hormonal shifts, and conditions that are specific to women. It also addresses different factors that play a role in women's health.

A girl is required to progress through different stages, during which her body experiences several anatomical and physiological changes, to reach maturity as a woman. There are numerous gynecological challenges that typically manifest in females during their reproductive years. Challenges related to reproduction can lead to difficulties in conceiving, which may result in emotional distress and obstruct family planning goals. Infertility and reproductive issues can generate emotional and psychological stress. Most diseases affecting women arise

from the dysfunction of the genital tract. These health issues in women are often a consequence of improper diet and lifestyle. This imbalance leads to the arrangement of the three Doshas: Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. The most common symptoms of gynaecological disorders include pelvic pain, vaginal itching, vaginal discharge, abnormal vaginal bleeding. The vitiation of Vata is primarily responsible for *Yoniroga* and *Artava Vikara*¹.

Thus, it is essential to normalize Vata first before treating other Doshas should be done. In Ayurveda, numerous local therapies, such as *Sthanika Chikitsa*, are recommended for managing common gynecological disorders.

Acharya has discussed *Chikitsa* in two segments - *Abhyantara Chikitsa* and *Sthanika Chikitsa*. "*Sthanika Chikitsa*" refers to targeted treatment administered locally. This form of treatment is advantageous when *Sthanika Dosh-Dusti* is prevalent, as it fortifies the corresponding *Sthana*. These localized therapies have demonstrated significant benefits in *Stree Rogas* when executed properly. While primarily a local treatment, their effects are systemic and can avert disease complications; thus, they are considered Para surgical since they do not require sharp instruments, helping to prevent the need for major surgery related to these conditions.

AIMS & OBJECTIVES

Aim: To understand the effective strategies of *Sthanik Chikitsa* in *Stree Roga*.

Objective: 1. To analyze the detailed procedures involved in *Sthanik Chikitsa*.

2. To study the probable mode of action of different *Sthanik Chikitsa*.

3. To explore the impact of *Sthanik Chikitsa* on genital health issues.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our Acharyas very well know the mode of action of this *Sthanika Chikitsa* and describe the specific *Sthanika Chikitsa* according to different *Yoni-Vyapad* or vitiated Doshas. These *Sthanika Chikitsa* (local therapies) are as follows. *Yoni Prakshalana*, *Yoni Pichu*, *Yoni Lepana*, *Yoni Poorana*, *Yoni Dhoopan*, *Yoni Varti*, *Uttar Basti*.

1. *Yoni Prakshalana* (Vaginal Douche)

Yoni Prakshalana is a procedure in which the vagina, vaginal passage, and mouth of uterus is washed with medicated decoction or other liquids. Medicated fluids or water should be filled in douche pot and vaginal douching to be done with rubber catheter attached with it. *Dhawan*

means cleaning or purification of wound with water or other medicated material, *Kwatha*, *Kshirapak*, *Ausadha Siddha Jala*, etc.

Sthana: *Prathamavra Yoni* (vagina)

Duration: 7 to 14 days after cessation of menses.

Position of patient during procedure: Dorsal lithotomy Drugs used in the form of - *Kwatha* (Decoction), Oil, *Kshirpaka* (Medicated milk), *Ausadha Siddhjala* (Medicated water).

Instruments Required: douche pot, Sterile Catheter, Cotton/gauze pieces, Hand Gloves

Procedure: Patient advised to lie down in lithotomy position for procedure, sterile rubber catheter can be inserted into vagina and vagina is washed out with decoction. Vulva should be dried up with cotton after completion of procedure and procedure can be repeated as per requirements.

Indications

Yoni Strava - With *Triphala Kwath*, *Karira*, *Dhava*, *Arka*, *Venu*, *Nimbi*, *Jambu*, *Jingini*, and *Sukta Kwath*

Yoni Paicchilya - *Rajavraksadi* group of drugs.

Yoni Kleda, *Dourgandhya* - *Aragvadhadi Gana Kwath*.

Yoni Kandu - *Guduchi*, *Triphala* and *Danti Kwath*²

Vataj artva dushti - *Sarala* and *Mudgaparni Kwath*

Pittja artva dushti - *Gairika* and *Nimb Kwath*

Kaphaj artava dushti - *Lodhra* and *Trikatu Kwath*

Mode of action - The drugs used for *Dhawana* are antiseptic, have bactericidal action, wound healing property, alleviates pain. Drugs are absorbed through mucosa and blood circulation of vagina. Bactericidal actions of the drugs prevent bacterial growth and maintain the pH of vagina.

2. *Yoni Pichu* (Vaginal tampons)

The term for the treatment is based on the *Sanskrit* word '*Yoni*', meaning 'genital tract'. The procedure involved in this treatment focuses on cleansing the vaginal area with the use of medicated *Ghrita*, *Taila*, or *Kashaya*.

The composition of pichu includes a sterile medicated cotton swab, which is wrapped in gauze, and fastened with an extended thread, taking the form of a *pottali*. It was immersed in medicated *Ghrita*, *Taila*, or *Kashaya* and then inserted into the vagina. These preparations fulfill two essential roles: *Shodhana* (purification) and *Ropana* (healing).

Types of Pichu: 2 types 1. Elongated 2. Circular Elongated: it is 4 finger length & 1 finger breadth Circular: 1 inch in length & breadth

Duration: 7-14 days after cessation of menses

Place: *Pratham Avarta Yoni* (Vaginal canal)

Pichu Dharana Kala: *Aamutra Vega* (Urge to urinate)

Position of patient during procedure: Dorsal lithotomy

Procedure

Poorvakarma

Pichu needs to be sterilized through autoclaving. It is essential for the patient to void urine before the insertion of Pichu. The patient should be placed in the dorsal lithotomy position.

Pradhaana Karma

Pichu soaked in medicated oil or liquid should be inserted into vagina with index finger of gloved hands. Thread of Pichu should remain outside the vagina so that Pichu can be removed easily.

Paschat Karma

The yoni pichu is retained until the patient has the sensation of needing to urinate. The patient can remove it by pulling the gauze tail after sitting in a squatting position.

Indications

Vataja Yoni Vyapad - *Guduchyadi Tail*,³ *Rasnadi Tail*⁴ *Saindhavadi Tail*⁵, *Til tail*⁶ *Dashmoola Tail*

Pittaj Yoni Vyapad - *Ghrita Soaked Pichu*, *Pachavalkal Siddha Taila*

Kaphaja Yoni Vyapad - *Triphla Kashaya* / *Udumbara Kashaya*

Tridoshaja Yoni Vyapad - *Dasanghri & Srimada Kashaya*⁷

Uppluta, Vipluta, Yoni Paicchilya⁸ - Dhatkyadi Tail⁹

Vipluta – Tagar, Vartakini, Kustha, Sandva, Amardaru Siddh Tila Taila¹⁰

Acharna, Vipluta, Vamini¹¹, Uppluta¹² - Shallaki, Jingini, Jambu, Dhav & Panchvalkala Kashaya Sidha Tail¹³

Paripluta Yoni Vyapad - Shallaki, Jingini, Jambu, Dhav & Panchvalkala Kashaya Sidha Tail¹⁴

Putraghni Yonivyapada - Udumbar Siddha Taila

Shweta Pradara- Nyagrodha twaka or Lodhra with Vata twak Kashaya dipped Kshom Vastra¹⁵

Yoni Vedana- Tagar, Vartakini, Kustha, Sandva, Amardaru Sidda Taila¹⁶

Yoni Paka-Pichu Dipped in Water of Chandana¹⁷.

Garbhini paricharya 9 month- Madhur Aushadh Siddha Taila¹⁸

Garbhastrava-Yashtimadhu Ghrita, Nyagrodhadi Gana Saddita Ksheersarpi, Ghrita & Ksheer.¹⁹

Aparasang - Shatpushpa, Kushtha, Madanphal, Hingu Siddha Taila²⁰

Mode of action -In the process of *Shodhana Karma*, *Pichu* contributes to the removal of slough. The oil used in conjunction with *Pichu* serves to strengthen the vaginal canal's musculature and supports wound healing.

3. Yonivarti (Vaginal suppository)

Varti is an extended and durable product that can be effectively utilized in treating infections and also offers the chance to restore optimal vaginal health. *Vartis*, which are suppositories, are created by combining finely powdered medications with adhesive substances or binding agents. The size of *Varti* should be equivalent to the circumference of an index finger and should be dried in a shaded area. Once prepared and thoroughly dried, *Vartis* are wrapped in a piece of gauze, and a thread is securely tied around it.

Size & shape: *Tarjani Anguli Pramana* (Index finger), *Yavakara*.²¹

Time duration: 1 Muhurta (48 min) or for short time period.²²

Paschat Karma: Wash with luke warm water after 1 *Muhurt* (48 min.).²¹

Procedure: For the procedure, it is advisable to utilize Autoclaved *Varti*. *Yoni Dhawana* must be conducted with lukewarm water while the patient is in the lithotomy position, following the voiding of urine. The expected component must be thoroughly cleaned, after which the oil-coated *Varti* should be positioned such that, the thread remains external. During the urine retention period, the *Varti* should be kept inside; when the patient experiences the urge to urinate, the *Varti* should be extracted, followed by *Yoni Dhawana* using lukewarm water.

Kaphaja Yonivyapada – *Yava/Maasa, Saindhav* and *Arkaksheer Varti*^{23, 24}

Varaha Piita Bhavita Vastra Samsodhini Varti^{23, 24}

Pipalli, Maricha, Masa, Satahwa, Kustha, and *Saindhav*^{23, 24}

Karnini Yonivyapada - *Kustha, Pippali, Arka, Rock Salt* and *Aja Mootra*²⁵

Anartava – *Ikshvaku Beeja, Danti, Chapla, Guda, Madanphala, Kinva, Yavashooka,* and *Snuhiksheera*²⁶

*Yoni Paichhilya*²⁷ - *Kasis, Triphala, Sphatika, Samnga, Lajjalu, Amrasthi, Dhatakipushpa* with *Madhu*

Acharna, Vipluta Yonivyapada - Piece of *kshoma vastra* dipped 21 time with Bile of Cow or Fish or *Kinva* Mixed with Honey.²⁸

Probable mode of Action: *Varti* is characterized by its prolonged and enduring nature. *Varti* can be effectively employed in the treatment of moderate vaginal infections and aid in preventing the reoccurrence of infection, as well as reestablishing the vaginal flora to sustain a healthy vagina.

4. *Yoni Lepana* (Vaginal Painting)

The finely ground substance is combined with water or a medicinal liquid to create a paste of uniform consistency, which is then applied locally to the affected area. Currently, it holds little importance in practice.

Type: *Pradeh, Pralep, Aalep.*

Timing: Until the *Lepa* dries.

Patient's position during the procedure: Dorsal lithotomy.

Procedure

The affected area should be cleaned, and the freshly prepared *Lepa* should be uniformly applied over it. Once it has dried, the *Lepa* must be removed promptly to prevent skin irritation, which may lead to rashes or itching.

Indications:

1. *Yonyarsha*- With powder of *Tuttha*, *Gairika*, *Lodhra*, *Ela*, *Rasanjana*, *Harenu*, *Pushpakasis*, salt mixed with honey.²⁹
2. *Vivrutta Yoniyapada* - With powder of *Palashbeeja* and *Udambarphala* mixed with *Tila Taila* and honey.³⁰

Probable mode of action: In *lepana* the drug penetration is higher on the vagina, the efficacy of *lepana* relates to both its inherent potency and the ability of the drug to penetrate the skin, muscles and mucosa. The drug utilized in *Lepana* possesses *Kashaya Tikta Rasa*, resulting in actions that are anti-inflammatory, antiulcer, anti-helminthic, astringent, facilitate the sloughing of dead cells, enhance blood circulation, and promote new growth while also providing strengthening effects. It aids in alleviating pain and burning sensations when used in conjunction with *Sheeta Dravya*.

5. *Yoni Poorana* (vaginal packing)

The term *yoni purana*, or *yoni dharana*, denotes the process of filling the *yoni* or holding dravyas within the vaginal canal.³¹ Various drugs, including *churna*, *kalka*, *veshvara* and *pinda* are compacted into a solid form and injected into the *yoni*. The active ingredients are absorbed through the vaginal or cervical epithelium, resulting in the intended action. Currently, it holds little importance in practice.

Site: *Prathamavart Yoni*.

Time: after cessation of menses for 7 -14 days.

Position of patient during procedure: Dorsal lithotomy

Duration: *Aamutra Vega* (Urge to urinate).

Indications

Mahayoni - with fat of bear, crab or cock and hog medicated with Madhura group of drugs^{32,33}

Prasansini Yoni - with *Vesawara* (minced meat or solid oleo mixed with drug)³⁴

Vesawara with *Shunthi*, *Maricha*, *Krsna*, *Dhanyaka*, *Ajaji*, *Dadima*, *Pippalimula*.³⁵

Udavarta, *Aticharana*, *Prakcharana*, *Antarmukhi*, *Sucimukhi*, *Sanda* - *Utkarika* made with *Yava*, *Godhuma*, *Kinva*, *Kustha*, *Satapusp*, *Srayahwa*, *Priyangu*, *Bala*, *Akukarni*.

Probable mode of action: The mechanism of action for the drug utilized in *Mahayoni* involves animal fat. Acharya Charaka states, "*Sarvada Sarvabhavana Samanyam Vrriddhi Karnam*," indicating that this theory supports the notion that animal fat contributes to nourishment or aids in the development of new tissues, thereby reinforcing pelvic musculature. Furthermore, it specifically designates animal fat for *Bhrista Yoni*, which refers to uterovaginal prolapse.

6. Yoni Dhoopana (fumigation of the vagina using medicated smoke)

It refers to the process of applying medicated smoke to the vaginal area. Fumigation can be performed on a specific wound, a particular body part, or the entire body based on necessity. This process involves exposure to smoke or fumes of any type as a method of disinfection or elimination. Additionally, *Yoni Dhoopana* serves the purpose of local disinfection of the genital organs.³⁶

Site- *Bahyayoni* (outer surface of vagina)

Time limit: 10-15 min.

Dhoopan drugs - *Kushta*, *Guggulu*, *Agaru*, *Vacha*, *Vidanga*, *Nimba* etc.

Procedure

A chair having hole in the middle is used and patient is asked to sit on this chair after voiding the urine, the *Dhoopana Dravya* are lit in *Dhoopana* apparatus which is placed just below the chair, the smoke coming from *Dhoopana* drugs must reach up to external genitalia.

Indications

Yoni Kandu – *Divai Haridra* and *Brahati Phala*³⁷

Shweta Pradara - *Dhoopana* by *Saral*, *Guggul*, *Yava*, *Ghrita* or *Katu matsyaka* with *tail*³⁸

Garbh Sanga - *Dhoopana* by *Krisna Sarp Nirmok* and *Pinditak*³⁹

Apra Sang - Dhoopana with Bhoj Patra, Kachmani, SarpNirmok⁴⁰ Krit Vedhana, Sarsap, Katuk Alabu, Guggulu, Kustha.

Sutika Paricharya - Dhoopana with Kushtha, Guggulu, Agar, Ghrita

7. Yoni Parishek:

Medicated oil, *Kwath*, lukewarm water is administered from a height of 4 to 5 inches above the vagina for the purpose of hot fomentation. *Parishek* is applied to the external area of the vagina for a duration of 5 to 10 minutes. This practice alleviates *Yoni Shotha* and *Yonishoola⁴¹*.

8. Kshara Karma (Chemical cauterization):

Kshara Karma, as offered by Ayurveda, is a para-surgical procedure identified as “*Anushastra*” in the *Sushruta Samhita*, utilizing alkaline preparations to facilitate *Chedana*, *Bhedana*, *Lekhana*, *Shodhana*, and *Ropana*. This approach is pertinent to *Garbhasayamukhagata Vrana* and *Karnini* conditions described in both classical and modern literature⁴². The *Sutra Sthana* of *Sushruta* refers to these strategies for the treatment of *Vrana*.⁴³

Indication:

1. *Yoni Arsha* (Genital warts)⁴⁴
2. Cervical erosion⁴²

Procedure:

Lithotomy position given to the patient. Vulva and vagina should be cleaned with povidone iodine solution. Cervix is exposed usingusco’s speculum. *Pratisaraneeya Kshara* is applied with a cotton swab stick over the eroded area and kept in contact for 30–60 seconds. Thereafter *Kshara Kshalana* (Neutralization) with lemon juice followed by *Jatyadi Taila Picchu*. Patient is advised to keep the Pichu for approximately 2 hrs. *Nimbu Swarasa* providing acidic neutralization to prevent deeper tissue damage and arrest the *Kshara* action.

Probable mode of action

Kshara possesses *Tikshna Guna* and *Ushna Virya*, characterized by a predominance of *Vayu* and *Teja Mahabhuta*. *Vayu* facilitates rapid action, whereas *Teja* induces a caustic effect. When *Kshara* (*Apamarga*, *Snuhi*) is applied to cervical erosion, it leads to the death of superficial

cells (due to vasoconstriction), the regeneration of basal cells (resulting in granulation tissue formation), and the growth of squamous epithelium in cases of cervical erosion.

9.Uttar Basti:

Uttar Basti is an essential para-surgical procedure among the *Shasthi UpKarma*, as indicated by *Acharya Sushruta*. *Acharya Charak* and *Vagbhata* have described Basti as *Ardha Chikitsa*. This treatment is particularly beneficial for *Vata Dosha*. “*Uttarena Margena Va Diyate Va Shreshtham Api Uttarbasti*”⁴⁵. The insertion of a medicated oil, *Ghrita*, Kwath into the *Uttarmarga*, which refers to the passage located above or in the front part of the anus, specifically the vagina (*Garbhashaygat*) or urethra (*Mutrashaygata*), is termed *Uttar Basti*.

It is essential to ensure that any previous infections are thoroughly treated prior to the application of *Uttarbasti*.

Time of administration - *Ritukala* (after menstrual bleeding stops / from 6th to 13th day of menstrual cycle)

Procedure

It is usually carried out under aseptic precaution in minor OT, no need of any anaesthetic agent or analgesic during and after the procedure. The patient is advised in dorsal lithotomy position. Cleaning with antiseptic solution done, cervix visualized with cusco's bivalve speculum, the IUI (Intrauterine insemination) cannula connected with 5 ml syringe and filled with Medicated *Ghrita* / oil and very slowly the medicated oil or *Ghrita* inserted in uterine cavity. *Pichu* is placed in vagina for 2 hours. Head low position should be given to patient and rest for half an hour.

Indication

Yonivyapada Chikitsa

*Vataja – Guduchyaadi oil, medicated oil with swaras or Kwath of Amla drvyas*⁴⁶

*Udavarta & Vatala – Traivritasneha*³²

*Karani, Acharana, Shuska,Prakcharna, Vipluta - Tail Siddha with Jivaniya Varga*⁴⁷

Arajaska & Putraghni - Ghrita medicated with the Kwath of Kashmari & Kutaja

Aparasang - Sidharathakadi Taila

Tubal disorders

Tubal block - If block is due to adhesions *Kshartaila Uttarbasti* is beneficial

Hydro-salpinx - *Nirgundi Taila*, *Yashtimadhu Taila*, *Til Taila* are used to manage this inflammatory condition.

Endometrial condition - *Sneha* prepared from *Bruhana Dravyas* helps in improving endometrial thickness.

Cervical erosion - *Triphala Ghrita*, *Shatavari Ghrita*, *Phala Ghrita* are the commonly used.

Vandhytva - *Phala Ghrita*, *Shatpushpa Taila*, *Lashuna Taila*, *Shatpak Taila*, *Bala Taila*, *Narayana Taila* ⁴⁸

Shukradushti

Probable Mode of Action

Theoretically, the drugs may reach into the uterus by the following mechanism:

1. Direct passive diffusion through the tissues.
2. Passage from vagina to the uterus through the cervical lumen.
3. Transport through venous or lymphatic circulatory systems.
4. Concurrent vascular exchange involving diffusion between adjacent utero-vaginal veins and arteries.

Uttar Basti functions to remove the *Srotosangha* and correct the *Artavagni*, which regulates the menstrual cycle and enhances ovulation by increasing the receptor receiving capacity of the ovaries connected to the H-P-O axis.

10. Nabhi basti /Nabhi Poorana⁴⁹

Nabhi basti synonymously mentioned as *Nabhi Poorana* in ancient literatures like *Charaka* and *Bhavaprakasha*. In classical texts of Ayurveda there is no direct references but it is mentioned among treatment modalities in contexts like *Atisara chikits* and *Udarachikitsa*. We also get reference of *Nabhipoorana* in folklore practices in abdominal colic and bloating. Procedure of *Nabhi basti* is similar as that of *Katibasti*, *Greevabasti* and *Karnapoorana*. Benefits of *Nabhi Basti* are *Snehana*, *Mrudu Swedana* and *Vatashamana*.

Procedure

The prescribed medicated oil should be warmed by keeping the vessel on hot water bath. After ensuring the tolerable temperature, oil should be poured inside along the sides of the dough. The temperature of the oil, should be maintained at 32-43°C by replacing a small quantity after reheating on hot water bath.

Indication

DISCUSSION

The probable mechanism of action of *Sthanika Chikitsa Prakshalan* is centered on cleansing, as all the drugs involved exhibit cleansing, bactericidal, and healing characteristics. *Pichu* aids in enhancing muscle strength, flexibility, and nourishing tissues. Yoni Purana is recommended in cases where the entire vaginal epithelium is affected, requiring a significant quantity of medication to prevent the uterus from descending. *Yoni Lepana* increases the surface area available for drug absorption, thereby improving the bioavailability of the drug due to its semi-solid consistency. The efficacy of *Lepana* is associated with both its intrinsic potency and its ability to penetrate deeper tissues. *Varti* is used to maintain pH levels, while *Dhoopana* is intended for disinfection. *Uttar Basti* is applied to nourish the endometrium, stimulate essential cervical secretions, and remove any obstructions. Consequently, all these local therapies possess the aforementioned properties, and the rich blood supply in the posterior fornix makes *Sthanika Chikitsa* effective in addressing *Yoni Vyapada* and other Stree Roga. The drugs are easily absorbed through the vaginal route, thanks to the highly permeable vaginal mucosa and the abundant blood supply in the posterior fornix, which is effectively managed by the intravaginal drug delivery system.

CONCLUSION

Sthanik Chikitsa, or local therapies, has demonstrated significant efficacy as a treatment modality due to its potency, safety, and cost-effectiveness. In the context of *Stree Roga*, it assumes a crucial role by directly targeting the affected area, thereby rectifying the underlying pathology. Various forms of medication, including *Kwatha*, *Taila*, *Ghrita*, and *Dhoom*, are employed; however, the advantages of these interventions are maximized when they are executed correctly, adhering to stringent aseptic protocols and appropriate indications. Consequently, it represents a promising and commendable treatment option for various Yonivyapad. Furthermore, it can be effectively integrated with oral therapies, contingent upon

the diagnosis, pathological condition, and accurate identification of the appropriate drug to be utilized.

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